

COMPARATIVE STUDY OF A BASIC AND MODIFIED MEMETIC ALGORITHM FOR THE ELECTRIC VEHICLE ROUTING PROBLEM

LUKA MATIJEVIĆ¹

¹ Mathematical Institute of the Serbian Academy of Sciences and Arts, Belgrade, luka@mi.sanu.ac.rs, 0000-0002-4575-6720

Abstract: *With increasing environmental concerns and the growing adoption of electric vehicles, green logistics has become a key area of research. This paper addresses the Electric Vehicle Routing Problem with time-dependent travel speeds, soft time windows, and partial recharging. The objective is to minimize total travel distance while penalizing deviations from customer time windows. We develop and evaluate two variants of a Memetic Algorithm, testing them on benchmark instances and presenting a comparative analysis of the results.*

Keywords: *GVRP, Green logistics, Metaheuristics*

1. INTRODUCTION

The *Vehicle Routing Problem (VRP)* is a well-studied combinatorial optimization problem, with numerous books and surveys dedicated to it. It can be viewed as a generalization of the *Traveling Salesman Problem*, extended to multiple salesmen (vehicles). A notable variant of VRP, which focuses on routing electric vehicles, is known as the *Electric Vehicle Routing Problem (EVRP)*. This variant was first introduced by and has gained increasing attention in recent years due to growing environmental concerns and the push for sustainable transportation.

Unlike *internal combustion vehicles (ICVs)*, *electric vehicles (EVs)* must visit *alternative fueling stations (AFSs)* to recharge their batteries. Moreover, while ICVs can refuel quickly, EVs require a longer time to recharge. This charging time must be explicitly considered when planning delivery routes, adding complexity to the problem.

This problem is computationally challenging to solve to optimality, as demonstrated in . For this reason, metaheuristic methods are commonly employed. A wide variety of metaheuristics have been proposed for solving similar problems, a comprehensive list can be found at the following [link](#).

In this paper, however, we focus primarily on the *Memetic Algorithm (MA)* and propose a slight modification to improve its performance on the EVRP. While the modification is tailored to this context, it is not entirely novel, we have previously applied it to enhance the training of neural networks.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 defines the specific variant of the EVRP considered in this study. In Section 3, we describe the standard MA as well as our *Modified Memetic Algorithm (MMA)*. Section 4 presents the computational results, and Section 5 concludes the paper.

2. PROBLEM DEFINITION

The problem addressed in this paper is an extension of the one studied in . It involves a delivery company operating a fleet of K identical EVs, all with the same speed, capacity, and energy consumption. Each day, the company receives a set of delivery requests from customers and must fulfill them as efficiently as possible.

Customers specify both the quantity of goods they require and a preferred time window for delivery. The company must then plan vehicle routes that respect these constraints, ensuring that the load on each vehicle does not exceed its capacity. Due to the limited range of EVs, vehicles may need to stop at AFSs during their routes. Unlike internal combustion vehicles, EVs take longer to recharge, so this factor must be carefully considered when scheduling arrival times at customer locations.

In the version of the problem considered here, partial recharging is allowed. This introduces additional complexity, as the algorithm must decide how much energy to recharge during each stop at an AFS.

Customer satisfaction is closely tied to adherence to the specified time windows. Delivering outside of

this window, whether too early or too late, may negatively affect customer satisfaction and risk future business. Arriving late may inconvenience the customer, while arriving too early could mean they are not prepared to receive the delivery. We consider *soft time windows*, meaning that vehicles are allowed to arrive outside the preferred delivery interval, but such violations incur a penalty in the objective function. To quantify these violations, we define a penalty function based on the arrival time τ_i at each customer $i \in V$. Early arrivals before the earliest allowable time e_i incur a penalty proportional to $\max(0, e_i - \tau_i)$, while late arrivals after the latest allowable time l_i incur a penalty proportional to $\max(0, \tau_i - l_i)$. The total penalty is calculated as a weighted sum over all customers, where α and β are user-defined parameters that control the relative importance of early versus late arrivals (in our case, both parameters were set to 1). This is expressed as:

$$\sum_{i \in V} p_i = \sum_{i \in V} [\alpha \cdot \max(0, e_i - \tau_i) + \beta \cdot \max(0, \tau_i - l_i)] \quad (1)$$

We also assume that all AFSs offer the same recharging rate and have unlimited capacity. Finally, this problem incorporates *time-dependent* vehicle routing, meaning that average vehicle speeds vary throughout the day, particularly relevant in urban environments where traffic conditions fluctuate significantly during rush hours.

3. MEMETIC ALGORITHM

The Memetic Algorithm is a variant of the Genetic Algorithm, originally proposed by . Its distinguishing feature is the integration of a local search (or refinement) step within the evolutionary process. This local search can be interpreted as an individual learning mechanism or as the cultural transmission of knowledge. Each individual in the population undergoes a learning phase aimed at improving its quality.

In our implementation, solutions are encoded as chromosomes, as illustrated in Figure 1. For the crossover operator, we employed the Order Crossover (OX) , a method specifically designed for permutation-based problems in genetic algorithms. The core idea of OX is to preserve the relative ordering of elements from the parent chromosomes while ensuring that the resulting offspring represent valid permutations.

Figure 1: Chromosome representation of routes

For the mutation operator, we introduce controlled diversification by applying a random number of modification actions to the solution. Specifically, an integer is randomly selected from the range $[1, 3]$, indicating how many mutation actions will be performed. Each action is independently chosen at random from a predefined set of five mutation types designed to modify customer assignments and route structures. The available mutation operations are as follows: $M_1(S)$ - relocate a randomly selected customer to a different position within the same route; $M_2(S)$ - move a randomly selected customer to a different route and insert them at a random position; $M_3(S)$ - swap the positions of two randomly selected customers within the same route; $M_4(S)$ - swap two customers selected from different routes; and $M_5(S)$ - transfer a customer to an empty route, if one exists and the maximum number of routes has not been exceeded.

As the local search procedure, we employed *Variable Neighborhood Descent (VND)*. The set of neighborhoods used within VND corresponds to those described in (Matijević, 2023a). Additionally, the methods for determining departure times from each node are also adopted from (Matijević, 2023a). We encourage the reader to consult that paper for further details on these methods.

The pseudocode for our version of the MA is provided in Algorithm 1, where the population size (N), number of offspring (NO), mutation rate (MR), and time limit for local search (VND_{limit}) are given as input parameters. This approach slightly deviates from the standard formulation of the MA, which typically relies on a crossover rate as a hyperparameter rather than specifying the number of offspring directly. For more detailed information on MA, the reader is referred to (Neri et al., 2011).

Algorithm 1: Memetic Algorithm (MA)

```
1: procedure MA( $N, NO, MR, VND_{limit}$ ) 2:   Initialize population of  $N$  individuals 3:   Evaluate fitness of
each individual
4:     while stopping criterion not met do
5:       offspring_set  $\leftarrow$   $\emptyset$ 
6:       for  $i = 1$  to  $\frac{NO}{2}$  do
7:         Select two parents using Roulette Wheel selection
8:         Generate two offspring via crossover
9:         for each offspring do
10:          Mutate with probability  $MR$ 
11:          Create the departure schedule
12:          Apply local search with time limit  $VND_{limit}$ 
13:          Add to offspring_set
14:        end for
15:      end for
16:      population  $\leftarrow$  population  $\cup$  offspring_set
17:      Evaluate fitness of all individuals in the population
18:      Select the top  $N$  individuals to form the new population
19:    end while
20:    return the best individual from the population
21: end procedure
```

The algorithm begins by initializing a population of N individuals (line 2), followed by evaluating their fitness (line 3). The main loop (lines 4-19) is executed until a stopping criterion is met (time limit in our case).

In each generation, an empty set is created to store offspring (line 5). Then, $\frac{NO}{2}$ crossover operations are performed (lines 6-15). For each iteration, two parents are selected using *Roulette Wheel selection* (line 7), and two offspring are generated via crossover (line 8). Each offspring is then subjected to mutation with probability MR (line 10), after which the departure schedule is determined to minimize penalties from violating time windows (line 11). Finally, the solution is improved using VND with a time limit VND_{limit} (line 12). The refined offspring are added to the offspring set (line 13).

After generating all offspring, they are merged with the current population (line 16), and the fitness of all individuals is re-evaluated (line 17). The next generation is formed by selecting the top N individuals (line 18). Once the stopping criterion is satisfied, the algorithm returns the best individual found (line 20).

Our *Modified Memetic Algorithm* introduces a key difference in the way local search is applied, while retaining the overall structure of the original method presented in Algorithm 1. As in the original version, the algorithm begins by initializing a population of N individuals and evaluating their fitness. In each generation, new solutions are generated through selection, crossover, and mutation, and stored in a temporary offspring set. However, unlike the original approach, where local search is applied to every offspring individually, the modified version applies local search only to the best offspring in the current generation. By focusing local search on the most promising solution, the algorithm intensifies the search in high-quality regions of the solution space without sacrificing too much time.

4. RESULTS

The experiments were conducted on a personal laptop equipped with an *Intel i7-10750H* processor and 32 GB of RAM, running *Ubuntu 20.04*. All proposed algorithms were implemented in C++ and compiled using *GCC 9.4.0* with the *O3* optimization flag to enhance performance. To ensure the reliability of our results, each test was repeated 30 times, demonstrating consistent outcomes.

We tested our methods on benchmark instances introduced in (Schneider et al., 2014), which are divided into two groups. The first group, referred to as I_1 , consists of 35 instances with up to 15 customers each. The second group, I_2 , contains 56 larger instances, each with 100 customers.

To model time-dependent travel speeds, we examined a scenario involving a goods transportation company based in Belgrade, which operates from 7 AM to 8 PM, totaling 13 hours of daily operation. We divided this delivery period into 13 equal subintervals, each assigned a distinct speed multiplier inversely related to traffic volume, as described earlier. Specifically, the first two intervals have a multiplier of 0.75, reflecting heavier traffic; the next eight intervals have a multiplier of 1, representing normal traffic conditions; the subsequent two

Table 1: The best-found values for each MA and MMA hyperparameter

Possible values	Hyperparameters			
	N	NO	MR	VND_{LIMIT}
	[5, 40]	[2, 20]	{0.1, 0.2, 0.3}	[1, 9]
2-5	MA			
I_1	25	17	0.3	4
I_2	6	3	0.1	7
2-5	MMA			
I_1	18	17	0.3	3
I_2	5	13	0.1	8

intervals have a multiplier of 0.8, indicating another period of heavier traffic; and the final interval returns to a multiplier of 1, corresponding to regular traffic flow.

To determine the optimal hyperparameter values for both the MA and MMA, we used the iRace package¹ within the R programming language. Each algorithm was given a budget of 1000 experiments per dataset. Table 1: shows the best-found hyperparameter values for MA and MMA, identified by the iRace package. The row labeled *Possible values* specifies the ranges from which iRace could select during the tuning process. The remaining rows report the selected values that yielded the best performance for each algorithm on the I_1 and I_2 instance sets.

In the evaluation conducted on the I_1 dataset, our analysis showed that MMA outperformed MA in 23 instances when comparing the **average solution quality** across runs. For these cases, the average improvement in solution quality was 45.8%, with differences ranging from 0.15% to 520.35%². Conversely, MMA produced inferior average results in 13 instances, with an average decrease in solution quality of 5.59%, and differences ranging from 0.56% to 27.75%.

A *Wilcoxon signed-rank test*, conducted at a 0.05 significance level and applied to the average solution values, confirmed that the performance difference between the two algorithms is statistically significant, with a p-value of $p < 0.01$.

When comparing the **best-found solutions** across all runs, a different pattern emerges: MA outperformed MMA in 27 instances, matched it in 4, and was outperformed in 5 instances. However, the magnitude of improvement reveals an important contrast: in cases where MA was superior, the average improvement in solution quality was 3.56%, while in the cases where MMA performed better, the average improvement reached a substantial 58.31%. This indicates that although MA more frequently found better best solutions, MMA achieved significantly larger gains in the instances where it excelled.

In terms of the **worst-found solutions**, MMA demonstrated superior performance, producing better results in 23 instances and worse results in 13. The average improvement in solution quality for cases where MMA outperformed MA was 109.36%, compared to just 7.05% when MA performed better.

A similar trend was observed in **average penalties**: MMA achieved lower-penalty solutions in 27 instances, matched MA in 5, and performed worse in 4. Interestingly, MA tended to find solutions with a lower number of routes, suggesting a different strategic preference in its search behavior.

When comparing the **average and maximum route durations**, no statistically significant differences were found between the two methods.

In the evaluation on the I_2 dataset, MMA demonstrated superior performance in 52 instances, while MA outperformed it in only 4. The average difference in solution quality also favored MMA. Specifically, in cases where MMA outperformed MA, the average improvement was 29.11%, with the smallest and largest gains being 3.12% and 55.41%, respectively. Conversely, in the few instances where MA performed better, the average improvement was 10.38%, with differences ranging from 1.25% to 18.62%.

¹ <https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/irace/index.html>

² We compute the relative improvement using the following formula:

$$\text{Improvement (\%)} = \frac{Z_{MA} - Z_{MMA}}{Z_{MMA}} \cdot 100$$

where Z_{MA} is the average solution value of MA, and Z_{MMA} is the average solution value obtained by MMA. Since the objective is to minimize travel distance, this formulation expresses how many times the MMA result is smaller than the MA result. For instance, an improvement of 520.35% indicates that the MA result is more than five times worse than the one obtained by MMA.

These results were further supported by statistical analysis, which confirmed a statistically significant difference in average solution quality between the two algorithms, with a p-value of $p < 0.0001$.

MMA also outperformed MA in terms of best-found solutions, worst-found solutions, and the number of routes. However, MA achieved better results in average route duration, maximum route duration, and total penalties.

Figure 2: A comparison between MA and MMA across several metrics on I_2

Figure 2 presents scatter plots of the results obtained from testing the instance set I_2 across various metrics. Points above the red line indicate instances where MA outperformed MMA, while points below the line indicate the opposite.

5. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we addressed the Electric Vehicle Routing Problem with soft time windows, time-dependent travel speeds, and partial recharge. The objective was to minimize both the total distance traveled by all vehicles and the penalty costs associated with time window violations. To tackle this problem, we developed and evaluated two memetic algorithms, one standard and one modified, on two sets of benchmark instances. The proposed modified Memetic Algorithm outperformed the standard version in most cases, demonstrating its effectiveness and potential for solving complex routing problems.

However, this study would benefit from further research, particularly by exploring a variant of the Memetic Algorithm in which the top α solutions are refined using local search, a strategy that was not examined in this work.

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